

Appendix A (Supplemental Figures)

An Integrated AI Knowledge Graph Framework of Bacterial Enzymology and Metabolism

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Fig. S1. Technical Elements Involved in IBIS-Enzyme and IBIS-Domain Training. This figure outlines the various neural network components, including Transformer blocks fine-tuned from ProtBERT, linear feedforward neural networks for classification tasks, and the application of Siamese contrastive learning for datasets with very few data points. Additionally, the figure presents the different training tasks and dataset sizes, with all tasks trained in parallel.

Fig. S2. Hierarchical clustering of bacterial genomes was performed using feature vectors that represent the percentage of required enzymes observed for each primary metabolic pathway. The analysis included feature vectors derived from 315 primary metabolic pathways across 52,584 bacterial genomes. Representative feature vectors for each metabolic group were projected into two dimensions using unsupervised UMAP. To enhance clarity and ensure distinct coloring, the visualization was limited to the twenty most abundant taxonomic families.

Fig. S3. Technical Elements Involved in IBIS-SM Training. (Top) The training process begins with a graphical representation of genomes organized as a network, where nodes represent genes associated with IBIS-Enzyme embeddings and edges denote nucleotide distances. This network is converted into matrix inputs, including a node feature matrix, an edge feature matrix, and an adjacency matrix that illustrates the connections among nodes. (Bottom) These matrices are then input into a Graph Attention Network (GAT) for message passing, which updates the generated node matrix by contextualizing the local neighborhoods of the nodes within the graph.

Subsequently, this contextualized node representation is processed by a transformer block to achieve global contextualization concerning the entire graph structure. The resulting representation of genes is then utilized in linear feedforward neural networks for classification tasks aimed at determining specialized pathways. See Fig. S25 for GAT-Graphormer details.

Fig. S4. Number of BGCs correctly identified from manually-derived genome boundaries by each of IBIS, PRISM, and AntiSMASH, including their overlap. BGCs are derived from the ‘15 genome’ dataset containing manually-annotated BGCs first introduced by Cimermanic *et al.* (19). The right side of the image represents the number of BGCs correctly identified by each tool, and the overlap between each of these tools. Each row in the table to the bottom right represents a single BGC-calling tool, with the colour of the circle indicating whether the tool is included or excluded by the BGC counts in the corresponding bar above. For example, the fourth column has filled circles for PRISM and IBIS, therefore the above bar represents the total number of BGCs identified by both PRISM and IBIS but not AntiSMASH. The bar chart in the bottom left represents the total number of BGCs correctly identified by each tool.

Fig. S5. Technical Elements Involved in IBIS-BGC Training. (Top) The training process commences with a graphical representation of a biosynthetic gene cluster (BGC), illustrating hierarchical levels: chemotypes indicated by labels as determined by IBIS-SM, proteins represented numerically by IBIS-Enzyme, and biosynthetic domains represented numerically by IBIS-Domain. A distinctive node corresponding to a BGC with a single label is introduced, serving as the representative embedding for the entire graph following processing with a transformer block (depicted as n_3 here). Nodes with labels undergo embedding lookups, resulting in individual feature matrices for each node type. These matrices are subsequently processed by linear feedforward neural networks to achieve uniform dimensionality and concatenated to form a comprehensive node feature matrix that represents the entire graph structure. Additionally, the edge types between each node are encoded as labels and processed through embedding lookups to generate an edge feature matrix (omitted for simplicity, but analogous to the node embeddings). An adjacency matrix is constructed to capture the connections among these nodes. The matrices are then passed to a Graph Attention Network (GAT) for contextualization of nodes relative to their local connectivity within the graph, followed by processing through a transformer block for global contextualization. (Bottom) The resulting node embedding for the BGC node is utilized for contrastive learning. Specifically, the square difference of a pair of embeddings is input into a linear feedforward neural network to predict the binned structural

relatedness of the two BGC-derived compounds. Training examples are binned according to Tanimoto molecular dissimilarity. The right-hand side demonstrates a potential prediction example for two highly related compounds. See Fig. S25 for GAT-Graphormer details.

Fig. S6. Experimental validation of the erythromycin GCF, which includes MiBiG BGC0000055. The Euclidean distance between the IBIS-BGC embedding of BGC0000055 and the IBIS-BGC embedding of the observed BGC is 7.34. The observed BGC is derived from *Actinopolyspora erythraea* DSM 45583, with the metabolite produced under STMS media conditions supplemented with 15% NaCl. The known structure of erythromycin matching the mass spectral data by mass and fragmentation is shown inset over the spectrum, with CFM-ID predicted MS/MS fragments inset adjacent to the peak CFM-ID predicts them to match.

BGC0001054 (*Xenocoumacin*) from *Xenorhabdus nematiophila* ATCC19061

BGC from *Photorhabdus luminescens* ATCC 29999

Fig. S7. IBIS-predicted BGCs for xenocoumacin/amicoumacin biosynthesis. (Top) The top BGC outlines the genetic arrangement of BGC0001054, which is associated with xenocoumacin biosynthesis (25). The bottom BGC represents the genetic arrangement of the related BGC identified in this work. The Euclidean distance between the IBIS-BGC embedding of BGC0001054 and the IBIS-BGC embedding of the BGC observed in *P. luminescens* ATCC 29999 is 7.57. (Bottom) Compounds named in bold-face represent known compounds; xenocoumacin I is associated with the known xenocoumacin BGC (25). The related known compound, O-methyl-amicoumacin, as well as two new compounds lipoamicoumacin E and diamicoumacin A were isolated and structurally characterized in this analysis (see “Isolation of the Amicoumacin Series of Compounds”)

BGC0000464 (Xenoamicin) from *Xenorhabdus mauleonii* DSM 17908

BGC in *Xenorhabdus szentirmaii* DSM 16338

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
Xenoamicin A	proline	butanoic acid	H
Xenoamicin I	glycine	proline	butanoic acid
Xenoamicin J	butanoic acid	H	--
Xenoamicin K	pentanoic acid	H	--

Fig S8. IBIS-predicted BGCs for xenoamicin biosynthesis. (Top) The top BGC outlines the genetic arrangement of BGC0000464. The area outlined in black represents the minimal region required for xenoamicin biosynthesis (26). The bottom BGC represents the genetic arrangement of the related BGC identified in this work. The Euclidean distance between the IBIS-BGC embedding of BGC0000464 and the IBIS-BGC embedding of the BGC in *X. szentirmaii* DSM 16338 is 3.84. (Bottom) The structure of the xenoamicin series of compounds, with the prototypical known compound highlighted in bold-face type. The three new compounds represented here are isolated and structurally characterized in this work, alongside xenoamicin A (see “Isolation of the Xenoamicin Series of Compounds”)

MiBIG BGC0000966

Observed BGC

Observed Metabolite

Fig. S9. Experimental validation of the caerulomycin GCF, which includes MiBIG BGC0000966. The Euclidean distance between the IBIS-BGC embedding of BGC0000966 and the IBIS-BGC embedding of the observed BGC is 6.55. The observed BGC is derived from *Actinoalloteichus cyanogriseus* DSM 43889, with the metabolite produced under KE media conditions. The known structure of caerulomycin matching the mass spectral data by mass and fragmentation is shown inset over the spectrum, with CFM-ID predicted MS/MS fragments inset adjacent to the peak CFM-ID predicts them to match.

MiBIG BGC0000880

Observed BGC

Observed Metabolite

Fig. S10. Experimental validation of tunicamycin GCF, which includes MiBIG BGC0000880. The Euclidean distance between the IBIS-BGC embedding of BGC0000880 and the IBIS-BGC embedding of the observed BGC is 4.27. The observed BGC is derived from *Streptomyces clavuligerus* DSM 738, with the metabolite produced under GGYM media conditions. The known structure of tunicamycin matching the mass spectral data by mass and fragmentation is shown inset over the spectrum, with CFM-ID predicted MS/MS fragments inset adjacent to the peak CFM-ID predicts them to match. We note that the stereochemistry of this molecule is presented relative to its isolated form and cannot be determined by this spectrum alone.

Fig. S11. Experimental validation of anthraquinone GCF, which includes MiBIG BGC0000196. The Euclidean distance between the IBIS-BGC embedding of BGC0000196 and the IBIS-BGC embedding of the observed BGC is 5.09. The observed BGC is derived from *Photorhabdus khanii* DSM 43369, with the metabolite produced under MM3 media conditions. The mass spectral match is confirmed by annotated MS2 spectra using CFM-ID. The known structure of anthraquinone matching the mass spectral data by mass and fragmentation is shown inset over the spectrum, with CFM-ID predicted MS/MS fragments inset adjacent to the peak CFM-ID predicts them to match.

Fig. S12. Experimental validation of bacillomycin GCF, which includes MiBIG BGC0001090. The Euclidean distance between the IBIS-BGC embedding of BGC0001090 and the IBIS-BGC embedding of the observed BGC is 1.60. The observed BGC is derived from *Bacillus subtilis* ATCC 19217, with the metabolite produced under TSB media conditions. The known structure of bacillomycin matching the mass spectral data by mass and fragmentation is shown inset over the spectrum, with CFM-ID predicted MS/MS fragments inset adjacent to the peak CFM-ID predicts them to match.

Fig. S13. Experimental validation of tauramide GCF, which includes MiBiG BGC0001796. The Euclidean distance between the IBIS-BGC embedding of BGC0001796 and the IBIS-BGC embedding of the observed BGC is 1.02. The observed BGC is derived from *Brevibacillus laterosporus* DSM 25, with the metabolite produced under MM3 media conditions. The known structure of tauramide matching the mass spectral data by mass and fragmentation is shown inset over the spectrum, with CFM-ID predicted MS/MS fragments inset adjacent to the peak CFM-ID predicts them to match. The stereochemistry of this molecule is presented relative to its isolated form and cannot be determined by this spectrum alone.

Fig. S14. Experimental validation of ornibactin GCF, which includes MiBiG BGC0002408. The Euclidean distance between the IBIS-BGC embedding of BGC0002408 and the IBIS-BGC embedding of the observed BGC is 2.19. The observed BGC is derived from *Caballeronia glathei* DSM 50014, with the metabolite produced under MM3 media conditions. The known structure of ornibactin matching the mass spectral data by mass and fragmentation is shown inset over the spectrum, with CFM-ID predicted MS/MS fragments inset adjacent to the peak CFM-ID predicts them to match.

Fig. S15. Experimental validation of photobactin GCF, which includes MIBiG BGC0002495. The Euclidean distance between the IBIS-BGC embedding of BGC0002495 and the IBIS-BGC embedding of the observed BGC is 6.24. The observed BGC is derived from *Photorhabdus stackebrandtii* DSM 43271, with the metabolite produced under MM3 media conditions. The known structure of photobactin matching the mass spectral data by mass and fragmentation is shown inset over the spectrum, with CFM-ID predicted MS/MS fragments inset adjacent to the peak CFM-ID predicts them to match.

MiBIG BGC0001757

IsnA 1.1 GTr
ORF 1 ORF 2 ORF 3

Observed BGC

IsnA 1.1 2.4
ORF 1 ORF 2 ORF 3

Observed Metabolite

Fig. S16. Experimental validation of rhabduscin GCF, which includes MiBIG BGC0001757. The Euclidean distance between the IBIS-BGC embedding of BGC0001757 and the IBIS-BGC embedding of the observed BGC is 3.80. The observed BGC is derived from *Xenorhabdus ishibashii* DSM 22670, with the metabolite produced under R2A media conditions. The known structure of rhabduscin matching the mass spectral data by mass and fragmentation is shown inset over the spectrum, with CFM-ID predicted MS/MS fragments inset adjacent to the peak. CFM-ID predicts them to match. We note that the stereochemistry of this molecule is presented relative to its isolated form and cannot be determined by this spectrum alone.

Fig. S18. Bacteria rich in genus-exclusive specialized metabolism, excluding bacteria with previously identified MIBiG compounds. 3709 GCFs exclusively produced by a single bacterial genus were considered for this analysis, after excluding genera found in MIBiG. The number of unique GCFs in each genus was normalized relative to the number of public genomes analyzed for all organisms with at least five public genomes. The top thirty organisms by normalized genus-exclusive BGC abundance are presented, with colors representing the relative chemotype distribution of each genus.

Fig. S19. A rhabdopeptide GCF statistically associated with the “Nematoda” isolation site. This GCF harbors examples of the rhabdopeptide and nematophin BGCs from MIBiG, which are shown as the first two BGCs in the Fig. Other examples of this GCF are demonstrated along with the organisms in which these BGCs are found. The isolation site metadata for each of these organisms is written in parentheses. The known structures for Rhabdopeptide, nevaltophin, and nematophin are shown to the right. In each BGC, grey circles with stand-alone ORF IDs represent individual proteins and are labeled with the first two digits of their enzyme commission number, first two digits of their KEGG Orthology number, or the relevant biosynthetic gene, detected by IBIS. ORFs bearing multiple circles represent domains. Abbreviations: C; Condensation, T; Thiolation, NMT; n-methyl transferase, Unk; unknown. Red circles represent adenylation domains integrating relevant amino acid substrates as predicted by IBIS-Domain and abbreviated as follows; Val; valine, MeV; N-methyl valine, N-M; N-methyl-leucine, Mopa; 3-methyl-2-oxopentanoic acid.

Fig. S20. Representative members of the *Streptomyces* GCF containing the known Thaxtomin BGC from MIBiG. The blue box indicates the location of the predicted NOS oxidase which is critical for Thaxtomin biosynthesis. The chemical structure of Thaxtomin is inset. Twelve other *Streptomyces* species harboring this GCF were identified in this analysis but had no isolation site information associated with their corresponding genome assemblies. In each BGC, grey circles with stand-alone ORF IDs represent individual proteins and are labeled with the first two digits of their enzyme commission number, first two digits of their KEGG Orthology number, or the relevant biosynthetic gene, detected by IBIS. ORFs bearing multiple circles represent domains. Abbreviations: C; Condensation, T; Thiolation, Unk; unknown. Red circles represent adenylation domains integrating relevant amino acid substrates as predicted by IBIS-Domain and abbreviated as follows: Leu; leucine, Trp; tryptophan, OH-; N5-hydroxy ornithine.

Fig. S21. Bacterial BGC Families Statistically Associated with BacDive Isolation Sites Using the IBIS knowledge graph. The Hypergeometric test was used to evaluate statistical enrichment of isolation sites in the producing members of all given GCFs. Any GCFs with enrichment in at least one niche, after multiple test corrections with the Benjamini-Hochberg method (5% FDR) were considered. The top 30 isolation sites with the most statistical associations are retained in the graph, as well as “wound” from which known BGCs with validated MIBiG BGC-niche relationships were derived. The dashed line on the vertical axis demonstrates where ordered ranking gives way to explicit selection of the “wound” isolation site.

Fig. S22. Enzyme Distribution for the Top 30 Microbial Genera Exhibiting the Highest Counts of Enzymes Not Assigned to Known Metabolic Pathways. The left histogram illustrates the allocation of enzymes to primary and specialized metabolic pathways, while the right histogram provides a detailed breakdown of unassigned enzymes based on their novelty, contingent upon their classification at the fourth level of the enzyme commission.

Fig. S23. Novel Pathway Distribution across Top 30 Microbial Genera. The right panel illustrates the distribution of enzymes across genera and the metabolic functions these enzymes were assigned by IBIS. Operons containing at least two unassigned enzymes were identified and embedded. Hierarchical density-based clustering was applied to group operons in the embedded space, with the number of computed families per genus displayed in the left histogram. Statistical enrichment of genera within the operon families was assessed using the Hypergeometric test, with a significance threshold set at a p-value of 0.05 after multiple test correction.

Fig. S24. An overview of the IBIS inference pipeline and its order of execution as it pertains to the analyses presented in this work. Fig. S1, S3, and S5 describe each of these models in detail and provide an overview for the mechanism of their training. (1) Firstly, protein sequences are embedded by IBIS-Enzyme, which creates protein embeddings representing the whole sequence (purple), as well as identifying regions in the protein corresponding to biosynthetic domains of polyketide and nonribosomal peptides (blue predictions). These regions are trimmed from the whole protein sequence, and passed to a second Transformer model, IBIS-Domain, which creates a domain embedding (green). (2) Secondly, protein and domain embeddings can be converted to human-interpretable labels using embedding databases containing reference embeddings. The inset image to the right describes the process of approximate-KNN annotation, wherein a protein embedding is related to its neighbours and the label of the query protein adopts a consensus label from its embedding neighbourhood. This approach is used to assign EC numbers, KEGG Orthology numbers, and gene family representations to proteins. This approach can also be used to identify related domain embeddings, and is how IBIS assigns substrate predictions to adenylation and acyltransferase embeddings, as well as determining ketosynthase, ketoreductase, enoylreductase, dehydratase, and thiolation biosynthetic subtypes (omitted for simplicity). (3) Primary metabolism decodes IBIS embeddings into relevant EC and KO annotations, and groups them according to curated rulesets. (4) IBIS-SM uses IBIS-Enzyme embeddings from all proteins in the genome to assign regions of specialized metabolism (i.e. BGCs) as well as their chemotype (orange). (5) IBIS-BGC incorporates embeddings and predictions from all other models to generate an IBIS-BGC embedding (red). This embedding is used to compare query BGCs to known BGCs (lower inset), as well as to cluster BGCs into families (GCFs; right inset).

Fig. S25. A general overview of the GAT-Graphormer architecture. This network is converted into matrix inputs, including a node feature matrix, an edge feature matrix, and an adjacency matrix that illustrates the connections among nodes. These matrices are then input into a Graph Attention Network (GAT) for message passing, which updates the generated node matrix by contextualizing the local neighborhoods of the nodes within the graph. Subsequently, this contextualized node representation is processed by a transformer block to achieve global contextualization concerning the entire graph structure.

Fig. S26. Structure of known compound O-methylamicoumacin B (**1**) and new compounds Lipoamicoumacin E (**2**) and Diamicoumacin A (**3**).

Fig. S27. Selected HMBC and COSY correlations of known compound O-methylamicoumacin B (**1**) and new compounds Lipoamicoumacin E (**2**) and Diamicoumacin A (**3**).

Fig. S28. ^1H NMR spectrum (700 MHz) in DMSO- d_6 of O-methylamicoumacin B (1).

Fig. S29. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in DMSO- d_6 of O-methylamicoumacin B (1).

Fig. S30. MS spectrum of O-methylamicoumacin B (1).

Fig. S31. ¹H NMR spectrum (700 MHz) in DMSO-d₆ of Lipoamicoumacin E (2).

Fig. S32. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in DMSO- d_6 of Lipoamicoumacin E (**2**).

Fig. S33. ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of Lipoamicoumacin E (**2**).

Fig. S34. HSQC NMR spectrum in DMSO-d6 of Lipoamicoumacin E (**2**).

Fig. S35. HMBC NMR spectrum in DMSO-d6 of Lipoamicoumacin E (**2**).

Fig. S36. ROESY NMR spectrum in DMSO-d₆ of Lipoamicoumacin E (2).

Fig. S37. MS spectrum of Lipoamicoumacin E (2).

Fig. S38. ^1H NMR spectrum (700 MHz) in DMSO- d_6 of diamicoumacin A (**3**).

Fig. S39. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in DMSO- d_6 of diamicoumacin A (**3**).

Fig. S40. ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of diamicoumacin A (**3**)

Fig. S41. HSQC NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of diamicoumacin A (**3**).

Fig. S42. HMBC NMR spectrum in DMSO-d₆ of diamicoumacin A (**3**).

Fig. S43. NOESY NMR spectrum in DMSO-d₆ of diamicoumacin A (**3**).

Fig. S44. MS spectrum of diamicoumacin A (3).

Compound	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
4	proline	butanoic acid	H
5	glycine	proline	butanoic acid
6	butanoic acid	H	--
7	pentanoic acid	H	--

Fig. S45. Structure of xenomicins A and I-K (4-7).

Fig. S46. Structure of ESI-MS fragmentations of xenomicin I (5).

Fig. S47. Select HMBC and COSY correlations of xenoamicin I (5).

Fig. S48. MS/MS spectrum of xenoamicin A (4).

Fig. S49. MS/MS spectrum of xenoamicin I (5).

Fig. S50. MS/MS spectrum of xenoamicin J (6).

Fig. S51. MS/MS spectrum of xenoamicin K (7).

Fig. S52. ¹H NMR spectrum (700 MHz) in Benzene-d₆ of xenoamicin I (5).

Fig. S53. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in Benzene- d_6 of xenoamicin I (**5**).

Fig. S54. ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum in Benzene- d_6 of xenoamicin I (**5**).

Fig. S55. HSQC NMR spectrum in Benzene-d₆ of xenoamicin I (**5**).

Fig. S56. HMBC NMR spectrum in Benzene-d₆ of xenoamicin I (**5**).

Fig. S57. NOESY NMR spectrum in Benzene-d₆ of xenoamicin I (5).

Fig. S58. ¹H NMR spectrum (700 MHz) in CDCl₃ of xenoamicin K (7).

Fig. S59. DEPT-135 ^{13}C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in CDCl_3 of xenoamicin K (7).

Fig. S60. ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum in CDCl_3 of xenoamicin K (7).

Fig. S61. HSQC NMR spectrum in CDCl₃ of xenoamicin K (7).

Fig. S62. HMBC NMR spectrum in CDCl₃ of xenoamicin K (7).

Fig. S63. NOESY NMR spectrum in CDCl₃ of xenoamicin K (7).